
**“MODERN APPROACHES IN NEW UZBEKISTAN MAJESTIC SCULPTURE
COMPOSITIONS”**

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8371629>

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Annotation

In the article, the new principles formed in modern sculptural compositions, practical, scientific and methodological researches, as well as the issues of aesthetic perception of Soha's sculptural works in the creative process, are widely covered.

Key words

art, creativity, composition, philosophy, work, modern sculpture, style, image.

In the sculpture of New Uzbekistan, modern compositions brought out new approaches, new methods of expression by interpreting both philosophical and psychological ideas in one composition. Of course, this process played an important role in the creation of interesting works by artists and sculptors. As humanity progressed, art developed or declined along with it to adapt to the spirit of each era. Some trends and currents have emerged. Even now, this process continues continuously, because art is related to the human spirit, mind, dreams and, of course, the politics of the time. Art always serves these elements, and with this we can easily study the politics of that time, the way of life of people. If we talk about sculpture from the types of practical art, it is difficult and heavy, requires strength and enthusiasm compared to other types of art.(1.2017y.1.06)

A sculptural model goes through several creative and technical stages from its creation to its final stage. Even a piece made in the workshop outside the workshop is greatly influenced by the natural environment, the surrounding landscape, and the light of the day. The created work may look completely different. At the beginning of the 20th century, the artistic life of Uzbekistan, especially the artists who lived in Tashkent, tried to apply the innovations of the artistic life of Petersburg and Moscow to their activities, led to the emergence of colorful currents and trends. As a result, the competition between artists who are loyal to the traditions of democratic art and those who want to create on the basis of Western methods has intensified. Attention to the harmony of art in the implementation of

large-scale construction works carried out in Uzbekistan today has also taken an important place in the development of sculpture.

The new plastic features that appeared in the modern sculpture of Uzbekistan had a significant impact on the development of the field. Especially, as a result of a free creative approach, the smoothing of the ways of incremental and compositional expression was one of the new results of this principle. Although this approach is not widespread, it is important as a result of modern creative research. The plastic expressiveness characteristic of three-dimensional sculpture was carefully mastered especially in the works of K. Norkhurozov and A. Hotamov. It is known that the majestic sculpture of the 1990s takes a worthy place in the initial process of the new historical period based on traditional and modern principles. (2.384b)

From the end of the 20th century, the rapidly developing technical progress and modern artistic processes taking place in the cultural life on a global scale began to provide new approaches in sculpture as well as in fine art. The process of globalization in world culture and art, the relations of electronic communication exchange (the development of the Internet and mass media), as well as the expansion of the scope of international exhibitions, are causing drastic changes in the minds of artists. It is important for every sculptor to choose a subject close to his heart. During his creative activity, the sculptor expresses this theme in various forms and compositions. For creative people, the symbolic expression of themes such as family, mother, creation, birth, and love is reflected in a completely new way. Of course, every work of art coming to the art field must acquire special significance with the story it tells. The presence of philosophical views in the compositions increases the viewer's interest in life.

The philosophy of life seeks to understand the essence of life itself. He glorifies feelings and instincts, criticizes and denies reason. According to supporters of the philosophy of life, the concept of life is complex, ambiguous, and does not have its own precise interpretation.

For the philosophy of life, time is important as the essence of creation, development and organization. And history appears in the Philosophy of Life as unique and unrepeatable "cultural organisms" that go through processes similar to biological periodicity from birth to death. At present, modern sculpture not only presents a trend of interdisciplinary development, but also increases its tolerance. It effectively embraces the achievements of installation, architecture and conceptual art. He can combine fine art and other visual methods into form and tries to incorporate time and process into the scope of contemporary sculpture, meaning

presentation. Zheng Lin, director of the Modern Tang Art Center, thinks that in the discussion of modern sculpture, the concept of sculpture should be changed from new, which can be divided into two categories: one is traditional or academic sculpture; the second one is the assembly works related to the experimental sculpture. (3.M.2018) The spiritual maturity of the creator is determined by the fact that the creative works created have their own spiritual significance in the society of individuals. In the end, every detail, even the smallest issue, requires a serious solution. as an important task, great attention was paid to the development of the industry, and great attention is being paid to this industry even now.

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